

D2.2 INTERIM IMPACT REPORT ON SUPPORT FOR EU PARTICIPATION IN RDA

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Dissemination Level

- PU: Public
- PP: Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission)
- RE: Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission)
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Glossary

Abbreviation	Definition
RDA	Research Data Alliance
ECRs	Early Career Researchers
IG	Interest Group
WG	Working group

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Executive Summary

The present deliverable outlines the work of the RDA EU project on the programmes designed to support the participation in RDA processes including activities of the Working and Interest groups, the RDA working meetings and workshops.

In particular, under the project WP2 “Support to European participation in RDA processes”, RDA Europe has developed and sustained three different platforms to engage and support the EU individual participation to RDA:

Grant	Focus	Total Grants foreseen (M1-M27)	Total Grants awarded (M1-M15)	KPI reference and progress to date
Early Career Researchers (ECR)	support for early career data researchers to engage with RDA	28	16	KPI 2.2 - on track
Experts	support for data professionals to support RDA WG / IGs	20	16	KPI2.1 - on track
Ambassadors	discipline-specific awareness raising and community engagement	12 + 2*	6 + 2*	KPI 2.3 - on track

Table 1 - Overview of grant programmes supporting individual participation to RDA

*2 ambassadors are supported as part of the national node contract with The Netherlands / DANS

Two of the programmes have a particular focus on supporting participation to the RDA working meetings, the RDA Plenaries, and the work of the RDA groups, for two specific categories of RDA membership: Experts and the Early Careers.

The third programme developed, the one dedicated to the Ambassadors, was, on the other hand, aimed at supporting participation by engaging specific discipline communities and building a two-way communication channel streamlining RDA outputs and contributions to domain communities and ensuring their vice-versa input in terms of requirements and best practices into the RDA.

This document outlines the different support programmes, the results and aspects related to the impact of these in relation to the RDA Europe 4.0 objectives especially:

Objective 2 – Providing the skilled, voluntary resources from the EU investment to address Digital Single Market (DSM) issues;

Objective 3 – Facilitating cross-disciplinary & multi-disciplinary research;

Objective 4 – Building, strengthening, and consolidating an RDA global community;

Objective 5 – Contributing to global interoperable data infrastructure;

Objective 6 – Democratizing access to funding opportunities in data infrastructures & interoperability.

1. RDA EU Early Career Researcher programmes

Currently at its 12th edition, the Early Career Researcher (ECR) programme supported through the RDA Europe project (ongoing and previous editions of the project) has become a platform to introduce early career researchers working with data to the RDA allowing them to share ideas, experiences and practical advice, while learning what leading data scientists and practitioners are currently working on.

This programme offers grant winners the opportunity to engage directly with and support the work of RDA Working and Interest Groups, to learn and contribute, and become a part of the RDA global data sharing community.

The programme is aligned with both the European project objectives as well as the RDA global vision of engaging a diversified and inter-generational community, supporting a new generation of leadership and fostering their opportunity to obtain expertise regarding data infrastructure while becoming well-connected at an early stage in their career¹.

The RDA EU Early Careers

The Early Career profile as outlined in the calls encouraged diversity while focusing on the career and study requirements:

- Currently engaged in Bachelor, Masters, PhD or Postdoc studies - applicants must be enrolled in a higher education study course or within maximum 5 years after completing a PhD in the case of Postdoc studies;
- Studies are/were conducted in a higher education or research institution based in one of the EU Member states or Associated countries
- Studies are of relevance to RDA Recommendations or Outputs and cover at least one of the Working or Interest Groups.

Grantees were selected based on:

- Area of interest, relevance of their work to RDA activities and foreseen benefits (criterion weight 60%);
- Proficiency in English (good knowledge of English is required to generate written content) (criterion weight 20%);
- Understanding of the European Data Infrastructures landscape, including initiatives such as the European Open Science Cloud; the FAIR data movement; knowledge of the Open Science agenda, and how these intend to evolve in Europe (criterion weight 20%);

All while considering the following criteria to establish balanced and diverse participation and distribution of grants:

- Geographical balance;
- Gender balance;
- Preference given to candidates who have not already previously received RDA funding;
- Preference given to candidates in underrepresented fields within RDA.

The ECR grantees

¹ <https://rd-alliance.org/get-involved/studentearly-career-programms>

At the time of writing this report, three editions of the grants programme were completed and a fourth one is currently underway, all timed with the RDA bi-annual working meetings (RDA Plenaries).

Ref.	Name	Surname	Country	Higher education Affiliation	Type of Study
11th Plenary ²	Louise	Grattarola	United Kingdom	University of Lincoln	PhD in Life Sciences
12th Plenary ³	Ana	Slavec	Slovenia	InnoRenew CoE Renewable Materials and Healthy Environments Research and Innovation Centre of Excellence	Post-Doctoral researcher
12th Plenary	Yasemin	Turkyilmaz-van der Velden	Netherlands	Erasmus University Medical Center, Rotterdam, the Netherlands	PhD in Molecular Biology and Genetics
12th Plenary	Maja	Dolar	Slovenia	University of Ljubljana	PhD in Business Studies
12th Plenary	Rossella	Aversa	Italy	CNR-IOM Istituto di Officina dei Materiali	Post-Doctoral researcher
12th Plenary, Nov 2018	Dorothea	Strecker	Germany	Humboldt University Berlin, Germany	Masters in Information Sciences
12th Plenary	Laura	Rothfritz	Germany	University of Applied Sciences, Potsdam, Germany	Masters in Information Sciences
12th Plenary	Martina	Trognitz	Austria	University of Heidelberg, Austrian Centre for Digital Humanities	PhD in Classical Archaeology
12th Plenary	João	Rocha	Portugal	INESC TEC	Post-Doctoral researcher
13th Plenary ⁴	Romain Olivier Marie	DAVID	France	National Institute for Agronomic Research (I.N.R.A.)	PhD in Environmental Information Systems
13th Plenary	Kathleen	Gregory	The Netherlands	DANS/Maastricht University	PhD in Science & Technology Studies

² 11th Plenary, March 2018, Berlin - <https://rd-alliance.org/plenaries/rda-eleventh-plenary-meeting-berlin-germany>

³ 12th Plenary, Nov 2018, Botswana - <https://rd-alliance.org/plenaries/rdas-12th-plenary-meeting-part-international-data-week-2018-gaborone-botswana>

⁴ 13th Plenary, April 2019, Philadelphia - <https://rd-alliance.org/plenaries/rdas-13th-plenary-meeting-philadelphia-us>

13th Plenary	Stephanie van de Sandt	Switzerland	CERN	PhD in Library and Information Science
13th Plenary	Tobias Weber	Germany	Leibniz Supercomputing Centre	PhD in Computer Science
13th Plenary	Daniela Hausen	Germany	University of Applied Science	Masters in Library and Information Science
13th Plenary	Stefan Reichmann	Austria	Graz University of Technology	PhD in the Social Sciences
13th Plenary	Joana Rodrigues	Portugal	INESC TEC	PhD in Digital Media

Table 2 - RDA EU Early Career grantees

ECR grant programmes in numbers

A total of 29 eligible applications were received and 16 grantees were selected. The table below illustrates the figures in relation to each Plenary and Open Call process.

Ref.	Eligible applications	Number of grantees	Countries represented	Gender balance
11 th Plenary, March 2018, Berlin	2	1	1 United Kingdom	1 Female
12 th Plenary, Nov 2018, Botswana	17	8	6 Slovenia, Germany, Netherlands, Italy, Austria, Portugal	6 Female / 2 Male
13 th Plenary, April 2019, Philadelphia	19	7	7 Netherlands, Germany, Switzerland, France, Austria, Germany, Portugal	4 Female / 3 Male

Table 3 - RDA EU Early Career grant programmes in numbers

Support to RDA processes - bringing forward diverse disciplinary perspectives

The evaluation process has also considered a broad domain and RDA groups coverage in terms of the disciplinary background and research interests of the selected candidates

<i>Grantees for the 11th Plenary – discipline coverage</i>
Natural Sciences/Biological sciences

Grantees for the 12th Plenary – discipline coverage

1 Engineering and Technology/Electrical engineering, electronic, engineering, information engineering
 1 Engineering and Technology/Materials engineering
 1 Humanities/History and archaeology
 1 Natural Sciences/Biological sciences
 1 Natural Sciences/Computer and information sciences
 1 Social Sciences/Educational sciences
 2 Social Sciences/Other social sciences

Grantees for the 13th Plenary - discipline coverage

1 Engineering and Technology/Electrical engineering, electronic, engineering, information engineering
 3 Natural Sciences/Computer and information sciences
 1 Natural Sciences/Earth and related environmental sciences
 1 Social Sciences/Educational sciences
 1 Social Sciences/Sociology

Table 4 - RDA EU Early Career programmes discipline coverage

Support to RDA Working and Interest groups

All grantees were assigned and introduced to three Working and /or Interest groups to support: note taking, meeting summaries, on site logistics, assistance to meeting coordination and other activities agreed with the group co-chairs.

Below is a snapshot list of the groups that have involved Early Career grantees in their activities

Grantees for the 11th Plenary – RDA WG & IG coverage

IG Early Career and Engagement
 IG Ethics and Social Aspects of Data
 IG SHARC IG

Grantees for the 12th Plenary – RDA WG & IG coverage

IG Disciplinary Collaboration Framework
 IG Early Career and Engagement
 IG Ethics and Social Aspects of Data
 IG Health Data / WG Blockchain Applications in Health
 IG Libraries for Research Data
 IG Metadata
 IG PID
 IG RDA/CODATA Legal Interoperability
 IG RDA/NISO Privacy Implications of Research Data Sets
 IG Repository Platforms for Research Data
 IG Reproducibility
 IG Research Data Architectures in Research Institutions
 IG Sharing Rewards and Credit (SHARC)
 WG BioSharing Registry
 WG Data Usage Metrics
 WG Data Versioning
 WG DMP Common Standards
 WG Empirical Humanities Metadata
 WG PID Kernel Information
 WG Provenance Patterns
 WG RDA/WDS Scholarly Link Exchange
 BoF FAIR Data and Open Science
 BoF GO FAIR

Grantees for the 13th Plenary – RDA WG & IG coverage

IG Active Data Management Plans
 IG Data Discovery Paradigms
 IG Data policy standardisation and implementation
 IG Disciplinary Collaboration Framework
 IG Domain Repositories
 IG Early Career and Engagement
 IG Ethics and Social Aspects of Data
 IG Libraries for Research Data
 IG Sharing Rewards and Credit (SHARC)
 IG Software Source Code
 WG Agrisemantics
 WG Data Citation
 WG Data Usage Metrics
 WG DMP Common Standards
 WG Exposing Data Management Plans
 WG FAIR Data Maturity Model
 BOF Coordinating Global Open Science Commons initiatives

Table 5 - RDA EU Early Career programmes WG and IG coverage

In addition to the practical support for the group working meetings, Early Career grantees have made active contributions or have taken on active roles in groups working and have pursued specific aspects related to their research as highlighted below:

Louise Grattarola: Working on a large and multidisciplinary collaborative initiative to establish a

model for a national system of quantification, management, storage and distribution diversity and conservation data while looking into aspects of education and research incentives as rewards.

Ana Slavec: Working on the development and implementation of the organisational data management plan and assisting other researchers with data collection, analysis, and reporting. Values RDA as the place to address issues such as the a lack of disciplinary repositories for the research areas such as renewable materials.

Yasemin Turkyilmaz-van der Velden: PhD candidate and one of the Data Stewards Delft University of Technology, involved in the Education and Training on handling of research data IG and the Active Data Management Plans IG - both in light of her role at TU Delft.

Maja Dolinar: Works on a PhD research project on "Sustainability of Open Research Data for Marketing Research". At the same time she is Head of Digital Preservation at the Social Science Data Archives - ADP working on work are open data policies, trustworthy data archive policies, and long-term data preservation management.

Rossella Aversa: was particularly interested in Research Data Architectures in Research Institutions and Domain Repositories interest groups both matching work around building up a distributed repository for the nanoscience community within the NFFA-Europe project.

Dorothea Strecker: Has collected input form the joint groups meeting on "Shareable Data: Metadata, issues of Privacy and Legal implications" for her work legal implications of sharing data and has outline the group developments as positive steps towards implementing legal metadata in machine actionable DMPs and facilitating informed decision making based on metadata while addressing legal uncertainty.

Laura Rothfritz: Currently pursuing a Masters degree in Information Sciences at the Applied University Potsdam working on quality criteria for research data (management), following closely the work of the WDS/RDA Assessment of Data Fitness for Use Wg and the Active Data Management Plans Interest Group.

Martina Trognitz: Collected feedback on the steps she and her colleagues at the Austrian Centre for Digital Humanities have adopted in establishing a digital long-term archive for research data from the humanities, as well as submitting it for certification - aspects related to FAIR, certification, Data versioning and Usage metrics.

João Rocha: became chair of the Repository Platforms for Research Data IG - currently building a repository solution for his institution and is seeking feedback on the choices made, plans to set up a WG (driven by the RPRD IG) as a forum for discussion and comparison of research data management platforms.

Romain Olivier Marie David: Contributing to developing FAIR assessment grids and appropriate recommendations in the SHARC's IG and provide input in agriculture data related-groups as both closely connected to the work at INRA and related PhD project.

Kathleen Gregory: A Phd candidate working on open source search solutions for research data is actively involved with the Data Discovery Paradigms IG, she is co-author on the best practices article published as an output from the IG.

Stephanie van de Sandt: Working on a PhD project related to Data Usage and Software Source Code identification, tracking reuse of research data and software in publications and contributing to CERN's research data information infrastructures, such as the CERN Open Data Portal. Actively involved among other with the Data Usage Metrics WG.

Tobias Weber: Particularly contributing to the Data Usage Metrics WG, complementing his research

project on automatic quality assessment approaches, how well machines can assess the quality of research data compared to human experts.

Daniela Hausen: Enrolled in a MLIS focused on RDM for chemistry is actively participating the Chemistry Research Data IG, Sharing Rewards and Credits (SHARC) IG and Research Data Management in Engineering IG. Has actively worked on the Charter for the “Research data management in Engineering IG”.

Stefan Reichmann: Working on a Phd project on social & cultural aspects of Research Data Management, focusing on understand cultural preconceptions of research and publication practices in selected disciplines and address them to facilitate the introduction of local level support structures for RDM and OS such as repository services and training for researchers as well as students.

Joana Rodrigues: Working to assist researchers from different domains to organize, describe and publish their datasets but particularly interested in the work of the Long tail of research data IG and discipline focused approached to data curation in the long tail.

Supporting inter-generational and cross disciplinary knowledge exchange

All grantees have been encouraged to join the [Early Career and Engagement Interest Group](#) and the wider Early Career and Fellows network inside the RDA and take advantage of the various support activities including the Mentorship programme the group runs bringing together senior RDA members and researchers at the beginning of their career and more often than not, newcomers to RDA.

In addition to the support provided the Working and Interest group meetings, grant winners have also actively taken part in the Plenary poster sessions displaying a posters summarising their studies and areas of interest. This has provided grantees with an opportunity to speak to and share ideas with other RDA community members working on similar topics or disciplines, and learn from their experience.

Figure 1 - RDA EU Early Careers at RDA Plenary poster sessions

Upon completing their assignments, grantees provided a publishable summary of the Plenary, meetings and their experience and take-aways. All the reports have been published as blogs on the RDA website <https://rd-alliance.org/blog>. The table below provides links and authorship information for blog reports:

Blog / Report Title	Author
RDA P13 - Networking, IG Research Data Management in Engineering and DMP as an important topic	Daniela Hausen
RDA Thirteenth Plenary: The Early Career Experience	Joana Rodrigues
RDA 13: The Social and the Technical updated	Tobias Weber
Summary content of Agrisemantics WG (Breakout session RDA P13)	Romain David
A (not so) Early Career Researcher's Experience at the 13th RDA Plenary	Kathleen Gregory
Attending the RDA 13th Plenary Meeting "With data comes responsibility" as an Early Career Grantee	Stefan Reichmann
Experiencing the International Data Week 2018 in Gaborone	Maja Dolinar
Many precious first time experiences, thanks to RDA Europe Early Career Programme	Yasemin Turkyilmaz-van der Velden
My first RDA plenary and the IDW2018 in Botswana	Ana Slavec
Addressing legal implications of sharing data	Dorothea Strecker
#IDW2018 at Botswana: These are exciting times to get into research data management	Joao Rocha
All is FAIR in love and data - attending the 12th RDA plenary in Botswana	Laura Rothfritz
Four days at the IDW18 in Gaborone	Rosella Aversa
The International Data Week 2018 and my first RDA Plenary	Martina Trognitz

Table 6 - RDA EU Early Careers grantees blog / reports

2. RDA EU Expert programmes

The Experts grants programme was designed to support the active participation of European data professionals in a more advanced stage of their career with respect to ECRs. Detailed criteria for applicants included:

- Experts are broadly defined as mid-career or senior data professionals / scientists;
- Be involved in RDA as active member, participant, chair, or contributor to a WG or IG, especially in the past 12 to 18 months;
- Be proactive and willing to contribute to RDA Recommendations or Outputs testing and adoption activities in European institutions;
- Actively engage in Plenaries, national, and/or regional workshops and related initiatives;
- Have the ability to recruit collaborators across different segments of the European data community;

- Be part of an active data community and have a good understanding of the European Data Infrastructures landscape, including initiatives such as the European Open Science Cloud; the FAIR movement; knowledge of the Open Science agenda, and how these intend to evolve in Europe;
- Reside/work in one of the EU Member states or Associated countries

Grantees were selected based on:

- A statement describing their interest in and commitment to the vision of RDA, in-progress Working/Interest Groups and/or one or more existing RDA Recommendations and Outputs; plans for future involvement and expected benefits (criterion weight 35%);
- A summary of previous and current activities demonstrating their involvement and contributions to RDA related activities, Working/Interest groups, development and /or promotion and/or adoption of RDA Recommendations and Outputs in European Institutions (criterion weight 35%);
- Wider engagement with other initiatives and/or national activities (and the national RDA node, if applicable) belonging to the European Data Infrastructures landscape, including initiatives such as the European Open Science Cloud; the FAIR movement; and/or initiatives on defining and implementing the Open Science agenda at national and European levels (criterion weight 30%);

While considering the following criteria to establish balanced and diverse distribution of the grants:

- Geographical balance;
- Gender balance;
- Preference to candidates that have not already previously received RDA funding;
- Preference to candidates in underrepresented fields within RDA.

The Expert grantees

As in the case of the ECR Open Calls, 3 editions of the grants programme were completed and a 4th one is currently underway, all timed with the RDA bi-annual working meetings (RDA Plenaries).

Ref.	Name	Surname	Country	Affiliation	Working with the RDA groups
11th Plenary	Tomasz	Miksa	Austria	SBA Research	(Co-Chair)DMP Common Standards WG Data Security and Trust WG Data Citation WG Exposing Data Management Plans WG
11th Plenary	Eva	Méndez	Spain	Universidad Carlos III of Madrid	Repository Platforms for Research Data IG Libraries for Research Data IG Education and Training on handling of research data IG National Data Services IG

11th Plenary	Fotis	Psomopoulos	Greece	Institute of Applied Biosciences (INAB CERTH)	(Co-chair) Data Discovery Paradigms IG (Co-chair) Early Career and Engagement IG Software Source Code Identification WG
11th Plenary	Jimmy	Angelakos	United Kingdom	EDINA, University of Edinburgh	Exposing Data Management Plans WG DMP Common Standards WG FAIRSharing Registry: connecting data policies, standards & databases WG
11th Plenary	Heidi	Laine	Finland	University of Helsinki / Finnish Council of University Rectors UNIFI	Ethics and Social Aspects of Data IG Empirical Humanities Metadata Working Group Exposing Data Management Plans WG
12th Plenary	Fiona	Murphy	United Kingdom	Murphy Mitchell Consulting Ltd	(Co-chair) Exposing Data Management Plans WG (Co-chair) RDAWDS Publishing Data Workflows WG Data policy standardisation and implementation IG Mapping the Landscape IG
12th Plenary	Caterina	Caracciolo	Italy	Food and Agriculture Organization of the UN	(Co-chair) Agrisemantics WG Agricultural Data Interest Group (IGAD) Vocabulary Services IG Wheat Data Interoperability WG
12th Plenary	Justin	Buck	United Kingdom	British Oceanographic Data Centre	Small Unmanned Aircraft Systems' Data IG Persistent Identification of Instruments WG
12th Plenary	Hugh		United Kingdom	Royal Holloway, University of London	(Co-chair) RDA/CODATA Summer Schools in Data Science and Cloud Computing in the Developing World WG (Co-chair) CODATA/RDA Research Data Science Schools for Low and Middle Income Countries (Co-chair) Development of cloud computing capacity and education in developing world research IG

12th Plenary	Ian	Bruno	United Kingdom	Cambridge Crystallographic Data Centre	(Co-chair) Chemistry Research Data IG (Co-chair) Data Usage Metrics WG WDS/RDA Assessment of Data Fitness for Use WG
12th Plenary	Tomasz	Miksa	Austria	TU Wien	(Co-Chair)DMP Common Standards WG Data Security and Trust WG Data Citation WG Exposing Data Management Plans WG
13th Plenary	Anne	Cambon-Thomsen	France	CNRS	(Co-chair) Sharing Rewards and Credit (SHARC) IG Ethics and Social Aspects of Data IG
13th Plenary	Giuseppe	Fiameni	Italy	CINECA	Data Fabric IG Federated Identity Management Preservation e-Infrastructure IG
13th Plenary	Fotis	Psomopoulos	Greece	Center for Research and Technology Hellas	(Co-chair) Data Discovery Paradigms IG (Co-chair) Early Career and Engagement IG Software Source Code Identification WG
13th Plenary	Sophie	Aubin	France	Institut National de la Recherche Agronomique	(Co-chair) Agrisemantics WG Rice Data Interoperability WG Agricultural Data Interest Group (IGAD) Vocabulary Services IG
13th Plenary	Alex	Ball	United Kingdom	University of Bath	(Co-chair) Metadata IG (Co-chair) Metadata Standards Catalog WG Data in Context IG Libraries for Research Data IG
13th Plenary	Mervyn	O Luing	Ireland	Insight Centre for Data Analytics	Storage Service Definitions WG Array Database Assessment WG

Table 7 - RDA EU Expert grantees

Expert grant programmes in numbers

A total of 33 eligible applications were received and 16 grantees were selected. The table below illustrates the figures in relation to each Plenary and Open Call process.

Ref.	Eligible applications	Number of grantees	Countries represented	Gender balance
11 th Plenary	11	5	4 Austria, Spain, Greece, Finland	2 Female / 3 Male
12 th Plenary	12	5	2 United Kingdom, Austria	1 Female / 4 Male
13 th Plenary	10	6	5 United Kingdom, Greece, France, Ireland, Italy	2 Female / 4 Male

Table 8 – RDA EU Expert programmes in numbers

The discipline coverage has also been diverse:

Grantees for the 11th Plenary – discipline coverage
1 Engineering and Technology/Electrical engineering, electronic, engineering, information engineering 1 Humanities/Other humanities 1 Natural Sciences/Biological sciences 1 Natural Sciences/Computer and information sciences 1 Social Sciences/Sociology
Grantees for the 12th Plenary – discipline coverage
2 Natural Sciences/Computer and information sciences 1 Natural Sciences/Earth and related environmental sciences 1 Natural Sciences/Chemical sciences 1 Natural Sciences/Computer and information sciences
Grantees for the 13th Plenary – discipline coverage
3 Natural Sciences/Computer and information sciences 1 Natural Sciences/Biological sciences 1 Agricultural Sciences/Agricultural biotechnology 1 Medical and Health Sciences/Health sciences

Table 9 - RDA EU Expert programmes discipline coverage

The successful candidates, active contributors to RDA activities, were expected to provide a detailed report as part of the grant assignment. The reports published under the blog section of the RDA website covered various disciplinary and technical topics, giving an account of the group meetings attended as well as highlighting any adoption use cases (finalized or in progress) they are involved in, challenges and lessons learned.

Bolg / Report Title	Author
Attending the RDA 13th Plenary as an Expert – From Production to Adoption	Sophie Aubin
A summary of the 13th RDA plenary in Philadelphia from the perspective of an expert grant awardee.	Mervyn O Luing
Make RDA fair again	Giuseppe Fiameni
Highlights from RDA P13 from Anne Cambon-Thomsen, thanks to an expert grant to attend	Anne Cambon Thomsen
Building standards in responsibility	Fotis Psomopoulos
The Joint Meeting of the Metadata Groups at the 13th RDA Plenary	Alex Ball
RDA connecting people (also at airports!)	Tomasz Miksa
The RDA 12th Plenary meeting in Gaborone: Insights for Training from Africa	Hugh Shanahan
Botswana... but that's landlocked!	Justin Buck
A Truly Awesome Meeting, IDW Botswana, November 2018	Fiona Murphy
Advancing Digital Frontiers of Crystallography, Chemistry and Research Data in Botswana	Jan Bruno
RDA 11th Plenary Berlin: Active DMP excitement	Jimmy Angelakos
From a “newbie” to an “expert” in less than two years - how to engage in the RDA activities?	Tomasz Miksa

Table 10 - RDA EU Expert grantees blogs / reports

Furthermore, Expert grant winners were invited to and have signed up to support the Mentorship programme coordinated by the RDA Early Career and Engagement Interest Group. This way, the two grant programmes complement each other in the effort to foster inter-generational exchange between researchers at different career levels.

3. RDA EU Ambassadors programme

The Ambassador programme, running in two waves, covers a total of 12 grants targeting recognised domain experts and skilled communicators, serving as conduits between the RDA and the wider domain specific communities they belong to.

By ensuring this two-way communication, the programme supports awareness raising around the work and outputs of RDA and also aim to help discipline experts grow their network and collaborate with like-minded people and organisations.

RDA Europe is committed to providing Ambassadors with:

- operational support as well for the Ambassadorial work,
- support for the coordination,
- official acknowledgement of the role,
- support to increase the impact of their work, professional growth and recognition.

The RDA EU Ambassadors

The profile as outlined in the programme Terms of reference:

- An RDA Europe Ambassador is a recognised domain expert and skilled communicator, serving as conduit between RDA and the wider domain specific communities to which the Ambassador belongs.
- The Ambassador takes part in RDA activities and is supported to facilitate a 2-way communication and engagement channel: talking to data practitioners and organisations about the work of RDA to disseminate RDA information via informal and formal channels; and making sure input from domain/discipline specific community(-ies) is incorporated in the work of RDA and shapes its future agenda.
- The Ambassadors will make active contribution to defining and promoting what RDA has to offer to discipline-specific communities. The ambassadorial work is carried out according to a detailed work plan that demonstrates impact for the domain community as well as RDA. The work will be disseminated via discipline-specific and general RDA communication channels, including presentations, webinars, training sessions, surveys, articles and reports.
- The mandate as Ambassador starts upon the confirmed successful selection and appointment and will be supported for the full duration of the RDA Europe 4.0 project (ending 31 May 2020). Ideally the mandate extends beyond that.

Grants selection criteria:

- The candidate profile and a summary of previous and current activities as influencer or representative of a domain specific community, with particular attention to data-focused activities/achievements in the Open Science context (20%);
- Statement about how the candidate expertise and work with data and the data community in their discipline is aligned with the mission and goals of RDA (15%);
- A summary of previous and current activities demonstrating your involvement and contributions to RDA related activities, Working/Interest groups, development and /or promotion and/or adoption of RDA Recommendations and Outputs (15%);
- A work plan of activities to be performed as part of the Ambassador role detailing how these will impact not only the community practices but will also make a significant contribution in the context of RDA. Reference Key Performance Indicators should be provided for macro-activities supporting impact assessment (35%);
- Wider engagement with other initiatives and/or national activities (and the national RDA node, if applicable) belonging to the European Data Infrastructures landscape, including initiatives such as the European Open Science Cloud; the FAIR movement; and/or initiatives on defining and implementing the Open Science agenda at national and European levels (15%);

Two waves of were foreseen for the recruitments of the Ambassadors:

- September - November 2018
- February - May 2019

RDA EU Ambassadors Programme 1st wave and initial cohort in numbers

Ref.	Eligible applications	Number of grantees	Countries represented	Gender balance
1st wave	17	6	5 Denmark, France, Italy, Slovenia, United Kingdom	2 Female / 4 Male
Ambassadors supported by nodes*	-	2	1 Netherlands	1 Female / 1 Male

Table 11 - RDA EU Ambassadors programme in numbers

*2 domain Ambassadors are supported through the network of RDA EU national nodes, specifically the Node from the Netherlands, coordinated by DANS as the organisation has the necessary mechanisms and expertise to ensure the roles are covered by skilled candidates.

Meet the RDA Europe Domain Ambassadors

Distinguished experts connecting the RDA with domain focused data communities, promoting the RDA vision and results and bringing insights and practical contributions from domain communities into the work of RDA groups.

Meet the Ambassadors at
rd-alliance.org/rda-disciplines/rda-europe-ambassadors

Contact them at
rd-alliance.org/rda-europe-ambassadors-contact

Dr. Julien Barde
Domain: Marine Sciences / Fisheries
Research Interests / experience: interoperability of information systems to improve (spatial) data management on marine ecosystems (biodiversity or ecological observations and related environmental parameters)

Dr. Ricarda Braukmann
Domain: Social Sciences
Research Interests / experience: Multi-disciplinary background, focusing on policy and communication development activities for Open Science, sustainable Data Management and training for Social Sciences

Dr. Caterina Caracciolo
Domain: Agricultural Sciences
Research Interests / experience: Interoperability of statistical data in the area of agriculture, dealing with semantic technologies including vocabularies, taxonomies and ontologies

Dr. Sébastien Denvil
Domain: Earth Sciences / Climate modelling
Research Interests / experience: high performance computing and research infrastructures for numerical climate simulations, international standardisation and metadata for the climate community

Dr. Rene van Horik
Domain: Humanities
Research Interests / experience: digital preservation, research data management, research infrastructures and supporting services for digital humanities and Open Science

Dr. Ana Slavec
Domain: Engineering/ Renewable Materials
Research Interests / experience: data management for materials engineering focusing on developing and implementing policies for data collection, analysis and reporting

Dr. Nikola Vasiljevic
Domain: Earth Sciences / Wind energy
Research Interests / experience: optical remote sensing of the wind and data management; has led the development and application of the long-range WindScanner system for atmospheric and wind energy research

Dr. Shaun de Witt
Domain: High energy physics/ Fusion
Research Interests / experience: multidisciplinary background focusing on metadata standards and ontologies, long term data and information preservation, and provenance for trusted and sustainable research

Figure 2 - RDA EU Ambassadors - poster

Dr. Julien Barde

RDA EU Ambassador for Marine Sciences / Fisheries

Julien has started working with the IRD (French National Research Institute for Sustainable Development, <http://en.ird.fr/ird.fr>) in 2008 as an IT research engineer. The focus of his work is the interoperability of information systems to improve (spatial) data management on marine ecosystems (biodiversity or ecological observations and related environmental parameters). He is currently working on methods to implement FAIR Data Management Plans by using R programming language to comply with widely used standards for data interoperability (eg OGC standards). Julien co-chair of the Fisheries Data Interoperability WG makes the case in his grant proposal for the development of factsheets for adoption stories together with other Fisheries domain resources (data, code and generic workflows)

Dr. Ricarda Braukmann

RDA EU Ambassador for Social Sciences - (Supported through the RDA NL node)*

Ricarda Braukmann is working as program leader for the Social Sciences at Data Archiving and Networked Services (DANS). She is part of the policy and communication department and involved in various projects promoting Open Science and sustainable Data Management. Ricarda has, for instance, been involved in the creation of an online Research Data Management training module for early career scientists (see www.cessda.eu/DMGuide). Ricarda has a multi-disciplinary background in Psychology (BSc) and Cognitive Neuroscience (MSc), and she received her PhD in Developmental Cognitive Neuroscience from the Radboud University Nijmegen in the Netherlands in 2018. Ricarda is the author of the RDA for Social Sciences report, an initial output of her RDA Ambassadorial work, providing an overview of the RDA work that is specifically interesting for social sciences researchers <https://rd-alliance.org/rda-social-sciences>

Dr. Caterina Caracciolo

RDA EU Ambassador for Agricultural Sciences

Caterina Caracciolo works to improve the interoperability of statistical data in the area of agriculture. Her work deals with semantic technologies including vocabularies, taxonomies and ontologies. For the past 13 years she has worked as an information specialist at the Food and Agriculture Organization of the UN. Previously engaged with the development and maintenance of vocabularies for textual information (AGROVOC), she is now focussing on classifications for statistical data. She holds a PhD in Computer Science from the University of Amsterdam and a Masters in Philosophy from the University of Pisa. Caterina is co-chair of the RDA Agrisemantics WG and contributor to the Wheat Data WG - working with the FAO, e-Rosa project (e-Infrastructure Roadmaps for Open Science in Agricultural and Food Sciences) and GODAN.

Dr. Sébastien Denvil

RDA EU Ambassador Earth Sciences / Climate modelling

Sébastien Denvil is a research engineer at IPSL (CNRS) and has more than 15 years experience in climate simulations, High Performance Computing and e-science infrastructure. He is involved at the heart of international standardization dynamics and at the heart of building the research infrastructure for numerical climate simulations which supplied the 4th (2007), 5th (2013) and 6th (2020) reports of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC). Sébastien is a leader in the European and international climate data and metadata infrastructure community. He plays a key role in the EU IS-ENES3 project (Networking activity Work Package Leader on data/metadata), the Copernicus programme (Coordinator of the project delivering regional climate projections to Copernicus) and also within the French national CMIP6 initiative (leading the data/metadata and analysis initiative in

France).

Dr. Rene van Horik

RDA EU Ambassador for Humanities - (Supported through the RDA NL node)*

René van Horik works as project manager at Data Archiving and Networked Services (DANS). He is involved in projects in the field of digital preservation, research data management and digital humanities. Several projects are part of the H2020 program, such as EHRI (European Holocaust Research Infrastructure), the EOSC-hub research infrastructure and FREYA (aimed extending the infrastructure for persistent identifiers). René studied economic and social history and received his PhD in information science from Delft University of Technology.

Dr. Ana Slavec

RDA EU Ambassador for Engineering/ Renewable Materials

Dr. Ana Slavec is a researcher at the InnoRenew CoE where her main role is to support the development and implementation of the institute data management plan and to assist other researchers with data collection, analysis and reporting. She obtained a Ph.D in Statistics in 2016 from the University of Ljubljana where she has been employed as a research assistant at the Centre for Social Informatics and later at the Social Science Data Archives. She is the co-coordinator of the Open Science work group at The European Council of Doctoral Candidates and Junior Researchers (Eurodoc). Ana is collaborating with the RDA Materials Resource Registries WG on an update to the report produced by the group on the metadata standards for different materials that in its initial version doesn't acknowledge wood and other biomaterials.

Dr. Nikola Vasiljevic

RDA EU Ambassador for Engineering and Technology / Wind energy

Nikola is a researcher at the Technical University of Denmark, Department for Wind Energy. His range of responsibilities cover instrumentation development and metrology, data management, and data science. Since 2010 he has been working in the domain of optical remote sensing of the wind. Nikola led the development, establishment and application of the long-range WindScanner system, a mobile infrastructure for atmospheric and wind energy research. Since 2017 Nikola has a leading role in applying FAIR principles in the wind energy domain. He is representing DTU Wind Energy in various national and international data forums.

Shaun de Witt

RDA EU Ambassador for High energy physics/ Fusion

Shaun has extensive experience in the field of data management connected to astronomy, remote sensing, meteorology, climatology and particle physics. He has been involved in European projects related to RDM including EUDAT and is currently engaged with the European Open Science Cloud Initiative. His main interests lie around metadata standards and ontologies, long term data and information preservation, and provenance as key for the exploitation of today's results by researchers in the future, and essential to building trust in data.

4. Feedback on programmes - lessons learnt

Early Career and Experts Grants – survey

Following the grant programmes for the 12th & 13th Plenary Meetings 3, the project ran a short survey to collect feedback from the grantees aiming to improve various aspects of the upcoming editions.

Below a snapshot of the ratings provided by a sample of 10 grantees:

Figure 3 - RDA EU grantees survey results

Grantees were encouraged to give feedback to improve their experience, and we have incorporated, among others, these very good examples:

- ECRs introductory / coordination virtual meeting prior to the Plenary meeting
- Dedicated meeting for grantees - formal and informal
- Anticipate the call timing as much as possible to give more time for travel planning
- Pins / Badges to indicate / recognised grantees during the meeting

Based on feedback from the grantees, the external evaluators as well as the wider community, the Grants Committee has worked on continuously improving the support programmes in terms of the clarity of requirements and criteria, application process, FAQs and online support, evaluation process, grantees support and coordination activities.

Furthermore, the Grants Committee is monitoring aspects related to discipline and WG and IG coverage and works on engaging underrepresented communities and disciplines in order to provide a balanced distribution of funds and improved representation. Statistics on coverage are collected and new iterations of the grant programmes have been aimed at addressing the gaps.